

Research Paper

Role of Mechanical CPR in management of Cardiac Arrest

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Abstract

Cardiac arrest, remains, the commonest cause, of sudden death. Research, led to the, introduction, of cardiopulmonary resuscitation, several decades ago, and efforts, continued, as to, how, its various aspects, can be, improved upon. This led, to the introduction, of techniques, protocols, medications, equipment, and guidelines, that, became increasingly complex, as time passed. However, the percentage, of successful resuscitation, and, survival at discharge, has not, seen, any marked improvement. The American Heart Association(AHA), and International Liaison Committee, on Cardiac Resuscitation(ILCOR), has released guidelines, that stresses, the need, of quality CPR, which, has the potential, to improve survival statistics. Mechanical chest compressions, delivered by, automated equipment, has been introduced, in many emergency medical systems, to address, the issues, surrounding, quality of CPR. The author, of this paper, has conducted review, of available reports, to determine, how mechanical CPR, can play a role, in the management, of cardiac arrest, in different scenarios, and its applicability to remote area healthcare projects.

Role of Mechanical CPR in Management of Cardiac Arrest

Background

The condition

Cardiac arrest, remains, a major cause, of mortality, worldwide (Berdowski et al., 2010). The survival rates, for both, out of hospital cardiac arrest(OHCA), and, in hospital cardiac arrest(IHCA), in United States of America(USA), and Canada, shows, significant variation, depending on region (Nichol et al., 2008; National Reports by Year « MyCares, 2018), and, the trend, is still continuing, as per, the latest statistics available. The American Heart Association(AHA), in its recent guidelines, has stressed the need, to maintain, the quality of cardiopulmonary resuscitation(CPR), so that, the issues, contributing to variations, under different scenarios, can be adequately addressed (Kleinman Monica E. et al., 2015, p.5). Research data, is confirming, the fact, that, the quality, of CPR, can affect, the return of, spontaneous circulation(ROSC) and survival rates, at discharge. These include, optimum rate, of chest compressions (Feneley et al., 1988; Idris et al., 2015), adequate, depth of the compressions (Stiell et al., 2012; Vadeboncoeur et al., 2014), allowing full recoil, after compressions, reducing interruptions (Cunningham et al., 2012), and avoiding, excessive ventilation.

Several studies, have concluded, that these parameters, are often, not achieved, during CPR, by trained personnel (Abella et al., 2005). There, are several factors, contributing, to poor CPR quality, such as rescuer fatigue (Ochoa et al., 1998; Sugerman et al., 2009), inadequate

depth (Haque et al., 2008), frequent interruptions (Sutton et al., 2009), suboptimal rates (Abella Benjamin S. et al., 2005), etc.

The Proposition and Intervention

Efforts, have been, going on, for some time, to automate, some parts of, the manual processes, involved in CPR. Various devices, have been designed, to provide, chest compressions, during the resuscitation attempt. It, has been proposed, that these devices, will be able, to provide, and sustain, guideline based, chest compressions, will free the rescuer, to perform, other duties, relieve fatigue, maintain, the set parameters, better than a human, and minimise interruptions.

Objective

The objective, of this research paper, is to review, current scientific literature, and delineate, any possible advantages, that mechanical CPR, may offer, during cardiopulmonary resuscitation.

Methodology

Search methods and criteria

The author, has used, Google Scholar, and PubMed Central, to search, for relevant articles. After, an initial database, containing adequate, variable pool of articles, the author, has considered, only those papers, that contain, statistical data. These include, animal studies, initial reviews, observational studies, randomised clinical trials, systematic reviews and meta-analyses.

Participants

All patients, irrespective of age and sex, suffering from, either OHCA or IHCA, are considered, provided that, the patient, has received, resuscitation care.

Interventions

Automated mechanical CPR device use.

Outcome

Any, significant variation, in survival percentage, has been considered, including, successful resuscitation, at the scene, survival to hospital arrival, survival to hospital discharge, and, up to 30 days, from discharge date. Neurological status, at each endpoint, is also, given consideration.

The Main Review

Animal and Manikin studies.

Initial experimental data, from animal, manikin, and human studies were promising. In, a canine model, the target parameters, were better, in mechanical CPR group than the manual CPR group (Wik, Bircher and Safar, 1996). In, another study, using porcine model, both, end tidal CO₂ and cerebral blood flow, were higher, in the mechanical CPR group (Rubertsson and Karlsten, 2005). Coronary perfusion pressure, and return of spontaneous circulation, were better, for mechanical CPR group, in this study(Liao et al., 2010).

Manikins, were adopted, for furthering, the experimental process. This study (Sunde, Wiks and Stein, 1997), concluded, that mechanical CPR, was superior, than manual CPR, in maintaining CPR quality, according to ERC guidelines.

Observational studies and Clinical trials.

Several years, have passed, and more data, is now available from various study designs. An early, prospective observational study(Krep et al., 2007), was highly optimistic, regarding, the future role, of mechanical CPR in OHCA. This retrospective study(Casner, Andersen and Isaacs, 2005), concluded that, mechanical CPR, may prove advantageous in non-shockable rhythms. Another investigation(Bonnemeier et al., 2011), concluded on similar lines. This recent, retrospective study, did not find, any significant, survival advantage, with the use, of mechanical devices, in OHCA(Newberry et al., 2018). Another, prospective randomized clinical trial(Perkins et al., 2015), did not find, any significant, survival advantages, with the use, of LUCAS-2 device.

Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses.

This, meta-analyses(Wang and Brooks, 2018), concluded, that data, is insufficient, to recommend, mechanical CPR, as, the preferred method, of chest compressions, and may be used, in exigent circumstances. This systematic review(Gates et al., 2012), did not find, any strong statistical evidence, for use of mechanical CPR, in routine, clinical practice. Another meta-analysis(Bonnes et al., 2016), also, did not find, any strong evidence, favouring mechanical CPR,

for routine use, in the field. Another, systematic review(Brooks, Bigham and Morrison, 2011), had, previously concluded, with a similar epitaph.

Special Circumstances.

Isolated reports, case studies, and special circumstances, were also considered. This report(Vatsgar et al., 2006), suggests, mechanical CPR, can be used, with success, for prolonged use, in cardiac arrest, after anaphylaxis, in pre-eclampsia. Another report(Holmström et al., 2005), reveals, success, in a case of, hypothermic cardiac arrest. This, case report series(Bonnemeier et al., 2009), indicates that, mechanical CPR, may be beneficial, in continuous CPR. Another vital finding, from, the cardiac catheterization laboratory(Wagner et al., 2010), strongly favours, mechanical CPR, when, prolonged resuscitation efforts, are required.

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Author's conclusions

To formulate, treatment protocols, and provide, definitive recommendations, it requires that, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses, identify, meaningful data. As of now, clinical trials, and reviews thereof, has not yielded, significant results. The author, concludes that, we will, need to wait, for, more experimental data, clinical trials, and analyses, to decide, whether, mechanical CPR, warrants a place, in routine clinical use. Improvements, in the design, and mechanism, of these devices, and, more user experience, may tilt, the balance, in their favour, in the future. The author, also concludes that, mechanical CPR, may still play a role, under exigent, and special

circumstances. The role of these devices in remote area healthcare projects will depend on the clinical context and relevant scenarios.

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